

True, False, or Uncertain?

Understanding Health (Dis-)Information Processing, Sharing and Assessment

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Abstract

The spread of health information that is false presents critical challenges for public health. This paper introduces a model of pathways of health information processing and sharing, derived through an app-based qualitative study with 155 participants over two rounds. The model illustrates how individuals process health information through pathways that are based on individual reflection and social interaction. Our findings challenge the binary view of information assessment, showing that participants often evaluate information on a spectrum, influenced by factors such as their own confidence, perceived quality of the information and contextual considerations. Participants frequently expressed uncertainty in assessments, reflecting the complexity of evaluating health information, particularly in ambiguous or emotionally charged contexts.

The study identifies five key information actions: assessing, researching, ignoring, sharing, and discussing, revealing motivations and barriers to engagement. The findings inform targeted interventions, including fostering nuanced evaluation skills, promoting transparency around uncertainty, and encouraging reflective practices before sharing information. This research offers a foundation for holistically understanding information behavior in health contexts and combating the spread of health disinformation.

Keywords: disinformation; information behavior; health information; diary study

1 Introduction

The spread of health disinformation is complex, occurring across multiple platforms including social networks, conversations, and traditional media. This phenomenon poses significant public health challenges, as false health information can lead to harmful medical decisions, vaccine hesitancy, and delayed treatment seeking. People share health information for various reasons, from personal relevance to social motivations, making it challenging to understand disinformation spread mechanisms. As Sharma et al. (2019) emphasize, it is crucial to identify environmental factors encouraging false information spread and explore connections between individual actions and broader disinformation dynamics.

Current understanding of how individual circumstances affect health information sharing remains limited. Most analyses are restricted to specific platforms like X or Facebook, or focus on single behaviors such as retweeting, providing incomplete insights into information sharing dynamics.

The DESIVE² – Understanding disinformation¹ project addresses this gap through a three-year study (2021–2024) funded by the German Federal Ministry of Education and Research. Using qualitative methods and grounded theory (Glaser & Strauss, 1967), the project investigates mechanisms of false health information spread, particularly regarding allegedly scientific information. This paper presents findings from an app-based study examining health-related false information, where participants documented real-life situations involving health information encounters and sharing.

Through this approach, we developed a model of health information processing and sharing pathways, contributing to understanding the complex dynamics of health information dissemination across diverse situations.

2 Literature and Motivation

In the DESIVE² project, we examine dissemination pathways and spread mechanisms of false health information. While Wardle and Dekrashaan (2017) distinguish between mis-, dis-, and malinformation based on creator intent,

1 <https://desive2.org/>

our project uses the broader term “false information,” acknowledging that intent is often unclear and can change along information pathways.

Information behavior encompasses all human interactions with information, including active, passive, and avoidant processes involved in monitoring, using, searching, sharing, discovering, and managing information (Wilson, 2022; Dewitz, 2022). While existing models typically focus on information needs and seeking behavior (Johnson & Case, 2012), few address false information spread. Notable exceptions include Karlova’s and Fischer’s (2013) Social Diffusion Model and Agarwal’s and Alsaeedi’s (2021) expanded framework, which incorporates misinformation mitigation strategies and factors like confirmation bias and filter bubbles.

Research on false information on social media is more extensive, with Aïmeur et al. (2023) providing a comprehensive review of detection approaches. Sharing motivations are diverse, including social media platform design, cognitive biases, and affective polarization (Lazer, 2018). Pennycook et al. (2020) found that social media platforms’ design can distract users from considering accuracy before sharing.

The COVID-19 pandemic highlighted the critical need to understand health-related disinformation. Islam et al. (2020) documented widespread misinformation on social media leading to severe health consequences, prompting WHO to characterize it as an “infodemic” (WHO, 2020). However, research examining individual instances of health information sharing remains limited.

Our research addresses this gap through a mixed-methods qualitative approach, focusing on app-based diary study outcomes. While Cacciatore (2021) identifies five main methodologies for analyzing misinformation, app-based approaches remain underutilized, despite a few studies that explore information behavior through digital journaling (Kümpel, 2022). Our study contributes by capturing in-situ interactions with health information, offering real-time perspective on sharing decisions (Perry et al., 2022), and helping identify patterns in health information behavior.

3 Method

The study used a custom-developed journaling and survey app to document health information encounters, focusing on two primary scenarios: (1) partic-

ipants sharing health information with others, and (2) participants receiving health information (Fig. 1).

Fig. 1 Two scenarios of health information sharing that were the basis for app development

The app captured three key elements: sharing motivations, relationship dynamics between information actors, and decision-making processes in information dissemination. Building on established media diary methodologies (Yurtaeva, 2017) we designed a research process of the app-based study illustrated in Figure 2.

Participants documented health information situations and answered standardized questions about sharing behavior, information sources, and information assessment (correct/incorrect/uncertain). To minimize biases, terms like “false information” or “disinformation” were avoided in app instructions. The study included three surveys (beginning, midpoint, and end) over a two-month period per participant. Incentives of up to € 70 were offered to maintain participation. The study received approval from the Ethics Board of the Humboldt-Universität zu Berlin and implemented data privacy measures in consultation with data privacy experts at Leibniz Information Centre for Economics.

Fig. 2 Illustration of the research process of the app-based study

The research was conducted in two rounds, as outlined in Table 1. Data analysis followed grounded theory principles, emphasizing iterative coding, constant comparison, and theory emergence. In the first round, two researchers conducted open coding, selective coding, and categorization of diary entries using MAXQDA, resulting in an interim codebook. These initial findings informed refinements in survey questions for round 2. The second round built upon this interim codebook, with continuous comparison, discussion, and refinement of codes executed by two researchers, again utilizing MAXQDA. Through merging and clustering, emerging themes were systematically evaluated until theoretical saturation was reached. This iterative process culminated in the development of a model describing health information processing and sharing pathways.

4 Data Analysis

The analysis presented here primarily draws on situations shared during the second round of data collection. The results from the first round are discussed in Stiller and Trkulja (2023). They played a critical role in refining the approach, questions, and survey design for the second round. Table 1 provides an overview of the data collected across both rounds, detailing the total

number of records for each data collection round. After a manual review, 272 uploads were grouped into distinct situations. In total, 252 situations, in which our participants stumbled upon health information in their everyday life and / or got send health information from someone, and their accompanying responses were analyzed for the second round.

Table 1:

Participants, uploads and number of submitted situations in the app study

	Round 1	Round 2	Total
Time period	15.03.23–31.07.23	16.08.23–14.01.24	
# of participants in app study whose contribution was part of the analysis	49	106	155
# of uploads	136	272	408
# of situations	116	252	368

Situations or their respective uploads shared by participants were accompanied by standardized questions. For understanding the data better, we firstly give some details about health topic, type of health information, medium in which the information was shared before presenting the dimensions that resulted into the model.

Health topics, types of health information, and medium of transmission

The study identified eight main health topics, with the most frequent being viral diseases/vaccinations (88 instances), diseases/ailments (69), and mental health/well-being (65). Within these topics, ten categories of health information were observed. The most common (98 situations) involved comprehensive coverage on single topics, regardless of its scientific rigor, such as comprehensive articles, reports, or videos. Health-related news ranked second (38 situations), including items like a Tagesschau² article on nursing competencies (T2841_297). Other categories included subjective health information (26 situations), often personal opinions or influencer content, advertisements (23), and scientific information (23), such as a Deutschlandfunk³

² Tagesschau is a German news program, produced by ARD.

³ Deutschlandfunk is a public radio broadcasting station in Germany.

interview on vegan nutrition (D3736_234). Less frequent categories included product information, health recommendations, memes, personal health information, and conspiracy narratives.

The medium of transmission was also analyzed based on how participants received the information. The most common channels were websites (81 situations) and social media (66 situations), with platforms like Instagram (33), Facebook (21), X/Twitter (7), and TikTok (5) leading the way. Messenger services such as WhatsApp and Telegram accounted for 24 situations, while traditional print media (16) and audiovisual media (11) appeared less frequently. In 16 cases, the medium could not be identified.

Situational analysis

We examined events and factors influencing the sharing or non-sharing of health information. In 133 situations, only the information itself was available, without context on sharing. In 95 cases, participants noted that the information was shared but did not provide details about the circumstances or impact. In 24 cases, the full context was documented, including the platform and communication framework, such as complete WhatsApp conversations (e.g., E547_406 (situation ID in MAXQDA) or G1769_391).

Additionally, the incident presented in the situation was coded. This coding was deliberately free and open to capture as many aspects of the situation as possible. In a second step, the codes were clustered without merging or dissolving the original codes. Therefore, there are many codes that were assigned only once. The aim was to categorize broad trends in the provided situation. Various actions associated with health information were described. For example, a health decision was made based on the information (e.g., H3365_226), or 15 participants reported “googling” health information. Many situations also describe ignoring information (47 situations). Overall, different types of actions emerged from this analysis: 1) evaluation of the information (relevance and validity and credibility), 2) researching, 3) ignoring, 4) sharing, and 5) discussing. These actions are not always clearly separable and can also overlap or occur sequentially. In Section 5, these findings are incorporated into a model.

Information assessment

Participants’ assessments of the information they shared or received were collected through two complementary methods:

1. standardized survey responses, where participants categorized the information as “true,” “false,” or “uncertain”
2. subjective assessments, based on free-form text and audio submissions, allowing participants to elaborate on their reasoning.

While the survey prompted participants to categorize information as either correct or incorrect, they were also given the option to indicate uncertainty. The responses reveal that information assessment often does not follow a strict binary logic, as many participants explicitly expressed uncertainty or provided more nuanced evaluations in free-text responses. Among the recorded sharing events, 105 cases were classified as correct, 76 cases were classified as incorrect, 46 cases explicitly selected uncertain. 17 additional cases contained nuanced assessments beyond the predefined categories, as revealed in qualitative responses.

While participants were asked to categorize information as correct, incorrect, or uncertain, their qualitative responses revealed a more nuanced evaluation process. Among the 157 subjective assessments, four key patterns emerged:

- Negativity (rejection/aversion): distrust of the source or perceived misinformation risks
- Uncertainty (hesitation/researching): skepticism leading to further verification
- Positivity (trustworthiness): confidence in the source rather than the content itself
- Lack of Personal Relevance: information dismissed as not applicable.

These findings demonstrate that information is not assessed in a strict true/false dichotomy but rather along a spectrum of skepticism, trust, and personal relevance, shaping whether individuals ignore, research, share, or discuss health information.

To illustrate the connection between the data analysis and the development of the model, Table 2 summarizes the key themes that emerged from the iterative coding process. The table outlines how open codes from participant data were clustered into categories, which were then synthesized into broader themes within the model. These themes – such as actions, assessing credibility, and the influence of emotions – represent distinct aspects of health information engagement identified in the study.

Table 2: Key themes and categories that emerged from the open coding

Themes in the model	Categories	Examples for codes from open coding
Actions: distinct behaviors in health information engagement	Ignoring	ignoring, waiting
	Discussing	counterarguments
	Researching	verifying information, googling symptoms
	Sharing	sharing with family, sharing with friends
Assessing credibility / validity / relevance	Assessing	trusts source, considered incorrect, considered correct
Assessing relevance	Sender-receiver relationship	sharing with close contacts sharing with distant contacts receiving from close contacts receiving from distant contacts
Assessing credibility / validity	Negative / Rejection / Aversion	scam, distorted, exaggerated, dangerous
	Uncertainty / Confusion	uncertain, difficult to assess
	Positive / Usefulness	true, useful, recommendable
	Lack of personal relevance	irrelevant, advertisement
Emotions: emotions influence health information engagement	Emotion-guided actions	sharing due to shock or outrage, resignation

5 Pathways of Health Information Processing and Sharing

Based on the analysis, we developed a situational model that generalizes the dynamics of information sharing. Figure 3 presents this model and connects several themes that play a vital role when health information is shared.

Fig. 3 Model of pathways of health information processing and sharing

Individual reflection vs. social interaction

Information processing begins with Individual Reflection (yellow elements), which may lead to Social Interaction (red elements). During reflection, a person evaluates information based on perceived relevance and quality. This initial assessment often occurs quickly and may be unconscious, influenced by emotions evoked by the information, its source, or sender.

The individual then proceeds to one of several possible information interactions: researching, ignoring, sharing, and discussing. Researching and ignoring typically involve solitary engagement, while sharing and discussing represent social interaction.

Assessing relevance and credibility and validity of information

When individuals encounter health information, they evaluate it based on relevance (personal or social importance) and credibility (perceived validity and trustworthiness). These assessments often overlap and occur along a spectrum rather than as a binary decision.

In our study, participants frequently considered information relevant if it affected them personally or applied to someone they knew. Emotional responses also played a key role – strong reactions (e.g., distrust of a conspiracy source or concern about misinformation risks) often led to deeper engagement, regardless of personal relevance (V4568_192).

Credibility assessments depended on confidence in one’s ability to judge information. When unsure, participants often experienced confusion or

sought additional sources rather than making a definitive judgment (F1986_222, H3365_225_226). This uncertainty reinforces that information is not simply classified as “true” or “false” but occurs on a spectrum.

After this assessment, one or several of the information interactions happen: researching, ignoring, sharing, or discussing.

Researching

Participants often researched information to verify claims, reduce uncertainty, or satisfy curiosity. For example, after receiving vitamin B tablets from a family member, one participant investigated their effectiveness and ultimately decided not to take them (H3365_225_226). Similarly, a TikTok video referencing a conservative news platform prompted another participant to fact-check via Google before forming an opinion (H3365_375).

Thus, motivations for further research range from reducing uncertainty, verifying information, to simple curiosity and a desire for knowledge.

Ignoring

Ignoring occurs when no further action is taken with health information, though it may involve superficial reflection. Participants often ignored information deemed irrelevant or unreliable, with no further steps like researching or sharing. In 189 of 252 analyzed situations, participants reported seeing or receiving information, but in 101 cases, no response followed. Common reasons included:

- Lack of relevance: Information was not personally applicable (e.g., hair loss prevention, S9680_262).
- Distrust: Skepticism toward unverified claims, conspiracy-related posts, or dubious links led to dismissal (e.g., vaccine misinformation on Facebook, G1769_340).
- Lack of time or interest: Participants planned to check later or dismissed content due to disinterest (F5634_394, N8278_235).
- Familiarity: Known information was ignored as it offered no new insights (e.g., COVID-19 updates, T2841_303).
- Perception as advertising: Content perceived as promotional or misleading was dismissed outright (e.g., knee pain relief patch, L4183_300).

Other factors, such as limited mobile data, also contributed to ignoring behavior (F5634_441). While ignoring does not mean the information was unnoticed, no further engagement occurred.

Discussing

When health information is not ignored, it often leads to social interaction through sharing or discussion. Discussions range from casual exchanges to critical engagement, influencing both individual and collective perspectives.

In some cases, participants actively countered misinformation. For example, a participant in a family chat challenged an article from reitschuster.de by highlighting its history of spreading false COVID-19 studies, prompting a debate (N8278_213). In another instance, a participant sent their father a YouTube video to debunk the myth that post-pandemic immune deficiency was making people sick (E5547_448).

Sharing

Sharing occurs either after reflection (e.g., sharing verified information) or as a quick, uncritical reaction (e.g., forwarding without assessment). Participants shared information they personally found or received from others.

In 38 cases, participants indicated passing on received information, primarily to friends and family, often based on relevance to the recipient's health. For example, a participant shared an onion and honey remedy for sore throats with others experiencing the same issue (K2434_182). Similarly, a news article on a cancer vaccine was forwarded to a friend with cancer (E9826_369).

Health topics were commonly discussed in family chats, especially with mothers and partners for shared health concerns (e.g., contraception, N8278_366). Sharing with acquaintances or colleagues occurred less frequently.

In summary, the model developed from our study captures the process of health information assessment, encompassing both individual reflection and social interaction. Through this model, we identify distinct pathways, namely assessing, researching, ignoring, sharing, and discussing, that illustrate how participants engage with health information based on relevance, quality, and personal or emotional factors. These pathways highlight the varied motivations and barriers that shape health information dissemination.

6 Limitation and Discussions

This study makes two main contributions. First, it introduces a model of health information processing and sharing, highlighting how individuals engage with health information through reflection and social interaction. Second, it challenges the traditional binary view of information assessment, showing that evaluations often occur along a spectrum. Participants identified nuances such as agendas, manipulation, and credibility, reflecting the complexity of real-world information processing.

However, this study has limitations. The reliance on self-reported data via an app may introduce biases, affecting the accuracy and completeness of responses. Situational factors, such as emotional state or social context, could not be fully captured, and the study's extended duration led to declining participant engagement, which may have impacted data consistency. These factors should be considered when interpreting the findings.

Despite these challenges, the results offer valuable insights for disinformation interventions. Given that participants assess information on a spectrum, educational initiatives could emphasize identifying dimensions like agenda, manipulation, and credibility. Training programs should promote a critical, multi-layered approach to evaluating information. The study also highlights participants' lack of confidence in assessing complex or controversial health information. Encouraging transparency around uncertainty and fostering a culture of seeking additional sources could help mitigate disinformation spread.

Moreover, as reflection often precedes sharing, interventions could nudge users toward more thoughtful engagement. For example, social media platforms could prompt users to evaluate their motivations before sharing health content, encouraging reflective behaviors. By promoting nuanced and reflective information assessment, this study lays the groundwork for empowering individuals to navigate health information landscapes with confidence and resilience against disinformation.

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